

THE USE OF METAPHOR IN ACADEMIC AND PROFESSIONAL DISCOURSE

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Annotation: This article defines that using of phenomenon of metaphor and metonymy in modern English. Moreover, many ways were shown how to present a broad overview of the phenomenon of metaphor and metonymy in modern English.

Key words: phenomenon, metaphor and metonymy, metaphonymy, analysis, metaphorization.

Introduction: The study of phenomena such as metaphor, metonymy and metaphonymy is a very relevant and important direction, both in the field of cognitive linguistics and in related fields. It allows us to visualize and understand the deep mechanisms of thinking and the formation of new meanings; how information is organized in consciousness and presented in language and speech; and gives an understanding of the process of language development as a whole.

Materials and methods: According to the Theory of conceptual metaphor (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980, 2003), metaphorization is based on the process of interaction between the knowledge structures (frames and scripts) of two conceptual domains - the source domain and the target domain. As a result of one-way metaphorical mapping from the source sphere to the target sphere, the elements of the source sphere, formed as a result of the experience of human interaction with the outside world, structure a less understandable conceptual target sphere. Metaphorical map is carried out between entire structures of conceptual domains, including separate elements of the two structures of knowledge. Let us explain the differences between the terms: metaphor as a linguistic structure, cognitive metaphor, conceptual metaphor and metaphorical model. Cognitive metaphor is a (cognitive) mechanism of thinking. Conceptual metaphor is the generally accepted correspondence of source and target. A metaphorical model is the result of the construction of cognitive processes, the result of which is a metaphorical expression. Thus, speaking of a metaphor in this chapter, we mean a cognitive metaphor as a cognitive mechanism of thinking, expressed in a scheme, conventionally called a model. In the classifications of metaphonymy by famous cognitive linguists, such as Goossens, Mendoza, and others, there are types that they call metaphor from metonymy or metonymic expansion (reduction) of a metaphorical source (target) (Mendoza). Several linguists state that many metaphors are based on metonymy.

Results and discussion: The conceptually unstructured referent of the metaphor correlates with the conceptually better structured correlate. In this case, the correlate and the referent should refer to different conceptual spaces. In Grady's Theory, primary metaphors are studied, in which the correlate and the referent are connected with each other within the framework of a specific sensory experience. As Grady says, they belong to the same conceptual space: the referent becomes a concept that is a "subjective response" to the sensory signal, information about which is presented in the metaphor correlate.

In primary metaphors, the referent is not more abstract than the correlate, and both are in the realm of the most fundamental, foundational experience we have. Primary metaphor demonstrates the connection between concepts that are equally "basic", both of which arise

from direct experience and perception. However, they are contrasted in terms of the degree of subjectivity of experience. Grady asserts, and a number of other linguists agree with him that these sensations are contiguous according to the principle "stimulus (correlate) - reaction (referent)". The correlate of the primary metaphor is an attributive concept, that is, it contains information not about objects, but about their properties that can be used in comparison (Lima, 2006)

- size, weight / severity, hunger, etc. The way in which the correlate and referent of the primary metaphor interact raises the question of its relationship with conceptual metonymy. Some linguists claim that contiguity in primary metaphor is very similar to metonymic one. And, as mentioned above, it is on the Primary Metaphor Theory that linguists base their belief that many metaphors are based on metonymy. We disagree with the statement that many metaphors are based on metonymy and we want to prove this by refuting the Primary Metaphor Theory.

Conclusion: The conclusions that we have presented above are confirmed by the analysis of the thinking process from perception to linguistic expression of a situation (event) and the formation of metaphonymy, which we give below. The basis of Gestalt psychology was the study of perception, which proved that we perceive the world around us in the form of ordered integral configurations, and not separate fragments. More scientists studied the psyche from the point of view of integral structures - gestalts. They proceeded from the position that all processes in nature are initially integral. Therefore, the process of perception is determined not by single elementary sensations, but by the entire "field" of stimuli impacting on the body, the structurally perceived situation as a whole (hence such a phenomenon as "syncretism"). Thus, relying on the research of Gestalt psychologists, it can be stated that the perception of a situation (event) is integral, undivided - gestalt (that is, metaphorical). Gestalt is a mental above conceptual phenomenon in which rational and sensual elements are combined.

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